

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BACTERIA FROM SOIL AND WATER SAMPLES ALONG WITH THEIR ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

Soil and water samples from college surroundings of JNTUA-Oil Technological and Pharmaceutical Institute were collected. A total of four isolates were identified in the soil and water samples, they are Bacillus, Staphylococcus, Enterobacter and Escherichia species respectively.

In view of bacterial resistance to antibiotics, we have tried with different antibiotics for susceptibility tests. Antibiotic susceptibility was determined by agar diffusion technique Mueller-Hinton (Kirby-Bauer modified disc diffusion technique) using nine different antibiotic discs corresponding to the drugs most commonly used in the treatment of human and animal infections caused by bacteria and all the four isolates were found to be sensitive to antibiotics which we have selected in the present study.

Key words: Bacterial resistance, Antibiotic, Soil and water samples.

INTRODUCTION

In microbiology, isolation refers to the process of separating a specific type of microorganism from a mixed population found in natural environments such as soil, water, or biological surfaces (skin, mouth, or intestine)[1]. The goal of this process is to obtain pure cultures that can be identified and studied for their structure, physiology, and potential applications. The inner layers of soil aggregates are typically rich in Gram-negative (-ve) bacteria, while the outer layers tend to contain more Gram-positive (+ve) bacteria. This difference may be related to bacterial motility, cell surface adaptations, polymer secretion, or various stages in their life cycle[2]. Bacteria are usually attached to soil particles or embedded within organic matter rather than existing freely in the soil solution. Soil bacteria are vital to several ecological and biochemical processes such as organic matter degradation, nutrient cycling, biogas generation, and nitrogen fixation[3-4]. Common soil bacteria include Agrobacterium, Clostridium, Arthrobacter, Bacillus, Nitrobacter, Corynebacterium, Nitrosomonas, Pseudomonas, Rhizobium, and Thiobacillus. A small quantity of soil can contain billions of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, algae, protozoa, and viruses, making it an excellent natural culture medium[5].

Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing:

Antibiotic susceptibility refers to the response of bacteria to antibiotics, indicating whether a specific drug can effectively inhibit or kill them. Because resistance levels can differ among bacterial strains, Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing (AST) is performed to determine which antibiotic is most effective for treatment[6-7]. A commonly used technique is the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, where small antibiotic-impregnated discs are placed on an agar plate inoculated with the test organism. If the bacteria are sensitive, a clear zone of inhibition appears around the disc. Other standard techniques include the Stokes method, E-test, and Agar or Broth dilution methods used to determine the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC). The compiled results are presented in an antibiogram, which helps guide appropriate antibiotic therapy[8-9]. The practice of microbial isolation originated in the 19th century in fields such as biotechnology and parasitology, and later extended to virology in the 20th century. Over time, technological advancements have made isolation techniques more efficient, automated, and accurate.

Description of Selected Bacteria:

Staphylococcus aureus

The bacterium Staphylococcus was first described in 1880 by Sir Alexander Ogston in Scotland after isolating it from an infected wound. Later, Friedrich Julius Rosenbach named

the species *Staphylococcus aureus*, derived from the Greek word *staphyle* (“grape cluster”) and the Latin *aureus* (“golden”), referring to its grape-like clusters and golden-yellow colonies. *S. aureus* is a Gram-positive, facultative anaerobic, round-shaped bacterium that is non-motile, non-spore-forming, and catalase-positive. It produces the enzyme catalase, which converts hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen. *S. aureus* is recognized as coagulase-positive, which helps differentiate it from other *Staphylococcus* species. Correct identification is crucial, as errors can lead to inappropriate treatment of infections.

Enterobacter Species

The genus *Enterobacter* includes species such as *E. aerogenes* and *E. cloacae*, which are opportunistic pathogens commonly associated with urinary and respiratory tract infections. *Enterobacter* belongs to the coliform group of bacteria but is not classified as a fecal coliform, since it cannot grow at 44.5°C in the presence of bile salts, unlike *E. coli*. *Enterobacter aerogenes* is a Gram-negative, rod-shaped, oxidase-negative, catalase-positive, citrate-positive, and indole-negative bacterium, typically measuring 1–3 µm in length. It exhibits motility due to the presence of peritrichous flagella.

Escherichia coli

E. coli is a Gram-negative, facultative anaerobic, non-spore-forming, rod-shaped bacterium that belongs to the genus *Escherichia*. The cells measure about 2 µm in length and 0.5 µm in diameter, and they grow optimally at 37°C. Most *E. coli* strains are harmless and are part of the normal intestinal microbiota of warm-blooded animals. They assist in producing vitamin K₂ and prevent colonization by harmful bacteria. However, certain pathogenic strains can cause foodborne diseases. *E. coli* is excreted through feces and can grow rapidly in fresh waste for several days before gradually declining.

Bacillus Species

Bacillus is a genus of Gram-positive, rod-shaped, catalase-positive bacteria that can live in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Many species are free-living in soil and water, while some are pathogenic. *Bacillus subtilis* serves as a model organism for studying bacterial genetics and physiology. Other species, such as *Bacillus anthracis* and *Bacillus cereus*, are significant pathogens responsible for anthrax and food poisoning, respectively [10-12].

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Materials

Sterilised apparatus (petriplates, test tubes, pipettes, conical flasks, measuring jar), burner, hot air oven, sterile water, chemical compounds for media, antibiotics and chemicals for biochemical tests.

Methods:

Sample collection:

A total of ten samples of soil from different locations and eight samples of water from surroundings of JNTUA-OTPRI were collected and stored in sterile test tubes with tight closures.

Preparation of water and soil samples:

One gram of soil sample was suspended in 10 ml of distilled water to make a soil suspension and then the suspension was diluted by serial dilution technique. Water sample was prepared by taking one ml sample and then it was diluted by serial dilution method. The media used in this project work was nutrient agar medium. Two grams of nutrient agar powder and other ingredients were weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of purified water. It

was stirred vigorously and dissolved using water bath and it was sterilised in an autoclave for 15 min at 121⁰C. Then it was poured equally and allowed to solidify.

Sample inoculation:

Portions of the prepared samples were inoculated on the nutrient agar medium by spread plate technique and they were incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours.

Spread plate technique:

0.1ml of sample inoculums was placed on the nutrient agar medium surface and was spread uniformly with a bent sterile glass rod. This will help in diluting the cell concentration in the inoculums. By this method cell aggregates get separated. This was incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours. After incubation, colonies were observed.

Sub culturing:

The isolated colonies of bacteria were sub cultured on plates containing nutrient agar media for short time preservation and to purify the isolates. The bacteria were inoculated using sterile wire loop as different designs of streaking on solidified sterile nutrient agar medium and incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours in incubator. This method is called as streaking plate technique[13].

Gram's staining technique:

Colonies which were grown on nutrient agar were identified by performing Gram's staining technique. Bacterial smear was prepared and heat fixed on sterile, clean dry slide using standard procedure. Few drops of crystal on the smear was added. Wait for one minute and washed with tap water. Now, the smear was flooded with gram's iodine after one minute and again washed with tap water. The stain was decolourised with ethylalcohol by dropping the reagent dropwise until crystal violet fails to wash from the smear. It was washed with tap water and counter stain with safranin for 45 sec and wash again with water. After it was completely dried, examine under oil immersion.

BIOCHEMICAL TESTS:[14]

Biochemical tests were used for the identification of bacteria species based on the difference in the biochemical activities of different bacteria. Bacterial physiology differs from one species to other.

Biochemical tests such as Phosphatase test, Mannitol fermentation test, Indole production test, Methyl Red and Voges-Proskauer (MRVP) test, Citrate utilisation test and Catalase activity test were carried to find out the enzymatic activity of isolated organisms.

(a) Indole production from tryptophan by the isolated bacteria :

There are some enteric bacteria that produce indole during the hydrolysis of tryptophan. Not all bacteria hydrolyse tryptophan through the production of tryptophanase but some hydrolyse. Indole production can be detected using Kovac's reagent that gives a cherry red layer of reagent.

Procedure :

Preparation of 1% tryptone broth : 10 gm of peptone was dissolved in 1 lit of distilled water and sterilised in an autoclave at 5 psi (121⁰C) for 15 min. Then inoculated tryptone broth with *E.coli* and another with *E. aerogenes* and kept third tube as uninoculated comparative control. They were incubated at 35⁰C for 48 hrs. After 48 hrs of incubation, add 1 ml of Kovac's reagent to each tube including control. Shake the tubes gently after an interval of 10 to 15 min. Allow the tubes to stand to permit the reagent come upto the top.

(b) Methyl red and voges – proskauer (mrvp) test :**Procedure:**

MRVP broth (pH 6.9) was prepared, 5 ml of broth was poured in each tube and sterilized in an autoclave at 15 lb pressure of 15 min. Two MRVP tubes with *E.coli* and two with *aerogenes* were inoculated and kept one tube as uninoculated comparative control. All 5 tubes were incubated at 35⁰C for 48 hrs. 5 drops of methyl red indicator was added to the tube of each set (*E.coli* & *E.aerogenes*).

(c) Citrate utilization test

Citrate test was used to differentiate among enteric bacteria on the basis of their ability to utilize or ferment citrate as the sole carbon source. The utilisation of citrate depends on the presence of an enzyme *Citruse* produced by the organism.

Procedure:

All the constituents except phosphates were to be dissolved separately in 100 ml of water, and made the volume to one litre. The pH was adjusted to 6.9. Media was poured in the culture tubes and sterilized by autoclave at 15 lb pressure for 5 min and prepare the slants. Simmon's citrate agar slant one with *E.coli* and another with *E.aerogenes* was inoculated, by means of stab and streak inoculation. The third tube was kept as an uninoculated comparative control. Then all the three slants were incubated at 37⁰C for 48 hours.

(d)Phosphatase activity:

Most strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* produce phosphatase and very few coagulase negative, *Staphylococci* produce phosphatase. For detection of the enzyme, *Staphylococcus aureus* is cultured on nutrient agar containing phenolphthalein di phosphate . On exposure to ammonia vapour, the colonies turn pink due to presence of free phenolphthalein. All strians found phosphatase- positive according to the conventional phosphatase test.

Procedure:

Agar medium containing phenolphthalein di phosphate was prepared and sterilised in an autoclave. The media was inoculated with bacterial culture and another petriplate containing media was kept as an uninoculated comparative control. Inoculated and uninoculated plates were incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hrs. After 24hrs incubation the plates were exposed to ammonia.

(e) Catalase activity:

Most of aerobes and facultative anaerobes have the characteristic of showing catalase activity. Actually, these organisms utilise oxygen to produce H₂O₂. The hydrogen peroxide is toxic to their enzyme system. Hence, these organisms produce an enzyme catalase which converts the H₂O₂ to water (H₂O) and oxygen (O₂). It is also that to the reason of not surviving an aerobes in the presence of oxygen is H₂O₂ and the absence of catalase enzyme.

Procedure:

A colony of bacteria was picked up from a plate and transfered the colony on a microscope glass slide in a drop of water. A few drops of 3% H₂O₂ were placed over the culture.

(f) Monnitol fermentation test:

Several media are available for these, most commonly used is phenol red monnitol broth. The medium is a nutrient broth to which 0.5 to 1% mannitol is added. The pH indicator phenol red is red at neutral pH but turns yellow at pH <6.8. It also changes magneta to hot pink at pH greater than 8.4. The purpose is to see if the microbe can ferment the carbohydrate (sugar) mannitol as a carbon source. If mannitol is fermented, acid and its

products decreases the pH of the medium. A pH indicator in the medium changes colour to indicate production.

Procedure:

An inoculum from a pure culture was transferred aseptically to a sterilised petriplate of phenol red mannitol broth. The inoculated plate was incubated at 35-37⁰C for 24 hours and results were observed.

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Evaluation of antimicrobial activity is done by using the following two methods.

1. Cup- plate method
2. Paper disc method

Antibiotics: Gentamicin, Penicillin, Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin, Cefotaxime, Amikacin, Streptomycin, Amoxicillin and Oxytetracyclin

Composition of nutrient agar medium:

Meat extract - 3gm

Peptone - 5 gm

Sodium chloride - 5 gm

Agar – Agar - 5gm

Distilled water - 1000ml

pH - 7.0

All the ingredients in a required quantity were weighed. Meat extract, peptone and NaCl were dissolved in distilled water. Then agar was added to the above solution and heated on water bath until agar was soluble in medium. Then this medium was sterilised in an autoclave at 121⁰C for 15 min.

By using paper disc method:

Procedure:

The agar medium was prepared and sterilized in an autoclave at 45⁰C. After sterilization, it was inoculated with the test organism and poured into sterile Petri dishes under aseptic conditions, then allowed to solidify. Solutions containing 100 µg/mL concentrations of various antibiotics were prepared separately. Filter paper discs were then soaked in these antibiotic solutions for about two minutes, dried, and carefully placed on the surface of the solidified agar medium. The prepared plates were kept in a refrigerator for **two hours** to allow proper diffusion of the antibiotics into the medium. Subsequently, the plates were incubated at 37⁰C for **18 hours**, after which the **zones of inhibition** around each disc were measured to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of the test organisms[15-18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table.1 The following table shows the results after applying Gram staining technique -

SAMPLE	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
Soil sample-1	Spherical shaped with violet coloured colonies were observed.	Indicates the organism may belongs to <i>Staphylococcus species</i> .
Soil sample-2	Small rod shaped with pink coloured colonies were observed.	Indicates the organism may belongs to <i>Escherichia species</i> .
Soil sample-3	Rod shaped chains with violet coloured colonies were observed.	Indicates the organism may belongs to <i>Bacillus species</i> .
Water sample-1	Rods shaped with pink coloured colonies were observed.	Indicates the organism may belongs to <i>Enterobacter species</i> .
Water sample-2	Spherical shaped with violet coloured colonies were observed.	Indicates the organism may belongs to <i>Staphylococcus species</i> .

Table.2 The following table shows the results of Biochemical tests-

TEST	<i>Staphylococcus species</i>	<i>Enterobacter species</i>	<i>Escherichia species</i>	<i>Bacillus species</i>
Phosphatase test	Positive	Positive	Positive	Positive
Catalase test	Positive	Positive	Positive	Positive
Methyl Red test	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Voges-Proskauer test	Positive	Positive	Negative	Positive
Indole production test	Negative	Negative	Positive	Negative
Citrate utilization test	Positive	Positive	Negative	Positive
Monnitol fermentation test	Positive	Positive	Positive	Positive

Table.3 The following table shows the results of antibiotic activity-

S.NO.	ORGANISM	ANTIBIOTIC	CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	INHIBITION ZONE DIAMETER (cm)
1.	<i>Staphylococcus species</i>	Gentamicin	100	2.5
		Penicillin	100	1.8
		Ciprofloxacin	100	2.4
		Erythromycin	100	2.2
		Cefotoxime	100	1.5
2.	<i>Escherichia species</i>	Amikacin	100	4
		Streptomycin	100	2.1
		Amoxicillin	100	1.7
		Gentamicin	100	3
3.	<i>Bacillus species</i>	Oxytetracyclin	100	2.4
		Gentamicin	100	2.8
		Ciprofloxacin	100	2.5
4.	<i>Enterobacter species</i>	Gentamicin	100	2.8
		Ciprofloxacin	100	2.5
		Streptomycin	100	2
		Amikacin	100	3.9

CONCLUSION

Four bacteria were isolated from ten soil samples and eight water samples; they are identified as *Escherichia species*, *Staphylococcus species*, *Enterobacter species* and *Bacillus species*. Their relative sensitivity towards antibiotics was determined. Relative sensitivity of bacteria towards antibiotics was in the following order:

- *Escherichia species*: Amikacin> Gentamicin> Streptomycin> Amoxicillin.
- *Staphylococcus species*: Gentamicin> Ciprofloxacin> Erythromycin> Penicillin> Cefotoxime.
- *Enterobacter species*: Amikacin> Gentamicin>Ciprofloxacin> Streptomycin
- *Bacillus species*: Gentamicin> Ciprofloxacin> Oxytetracyclin.

Amikacin was more potent than Gentamicin, Streptomycin and Amoxicillin against *Escherichia species*.Amikacin was more potent than Gentamicin, Ciprofloxacin and Streptomycin against *Enterobacter species*.Gentamicin was more potent than Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin, Penicillin and Cefotoxime against *Staphylococcus species*.Gentamicin was more potent than Ciprofloxacin and Oxytetracyclin against *Bacillus species*.We conclude that Amikacin was more potent antibiotic against *Escherichia species* and *Enterobacter species*. Gentamicin was more potent antibiotic against *Staphylococcus species* and *Bacillus species*.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors have no conflict of interest regarding this research work.

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